

OVERCOMING THE DIGITAL DIVIDE: THE PROBLEM OF EQUAL ACCESS TO EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. This article examines the digital divide affecting students at the Russian State University of Oil and Gas, named after Gubkin, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan, particularly focusing on the challenges faced by those residing in rural areas. As higher education increasingly relies on digital resources, the necessity for robust digital infrastructure becomes apparent. This study highlights the critical gaps in digital accessibility and explores the ongoing challenges students face in accessing educational resources online. Through qualitative research, including face-to-face interviews, this paper provides insights into the difficulties rural students encounter when trying to access study materials, stay updated with university news, and communicate with peers, especially during holidays and free time. The findings emphasize the need for continuous assessment and improvement of digital accessibility by higher education institutions, advocating for a strategic approach that incorporates both policy development and practical solutions to ensure all students have equitable access to educational technologies.

Keywords: digital divide, Educational equity, Rural education, Digital accessibility, Higher education.

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматривается проблема цифрового неравенства, с которой сталкиваются студенты Российского государственного университета нефти и газа имени Губкина в Ташкенте, Узбекистан, с особым акцентом на проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются жители сельской местности. Поскольку высшее образование все больше зависит от цифровых ресурсов, необходимость в надежной цифровой инфраструктуре становится очевидной. В этом исследовании подчеркиваются серьезные пробелы в доступности цифровых технологий и исследуются текущие проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются учащиеся при получении доступа к образовательным ресурсам онлайн. Благодаря качественному исследованию, включая личные интервью, в этой статье дается представление о трудностях, с которыми сталкиваются сельские студенты, пытаясь получить доступ к учебным материалам, быть в курсе университетских новостей и общаться со сверстниками, особенно во время каникул и в свободное время. Полученные результаты подчеркивают необходимость постоянной оценки и улучшения доступности цифровых технологий высшими учебными заведениями, выступая за стратегический подход, который включает в себя как разработку политики, так и практические решения для обеспечения равного доступа всех студентов к образовательным технологиям.

Ключевые слова: цифровой разрыв, равенство в образовании, сельское образование, Цифровая доступность, Высшее образование.

Annotasiya. Ushbu maqolada I.M.Gubkin nomidagi Rossiya davlat neft va gaz universiteti Toshkent shahridagi filiali talabalari duch kelayotgan raqamli tengsizlik muammolari ko'rib chiqiladi, ayniqsa qishloq aholisi duch keladigan muammolarga alohida e'tibor qaratiladi. Oliy ta'lim raqamli resurslarga tobora ko'proq bog'liq bo'lganligi sababli, ishonchli raqamli infratuzilmaga ehtiyoj ortib bormoqda. Ushbu tadqiqot ishida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishda mavjud bo'lgan jiddiy kamchiliklar sanab o'tiladi va talabalarning onlayn ta'lim resurslariga kirishda duch keladigan dolzarb muammolar yoritiladi. Maqolada sifatli tadqiqotlar,

shu jumladan yuzma-yuz suhbatlar yordamida qishloq hududlarida istiqomat qiluvchi talabalarning o‘quv materiallaridan foydalanish, universitet yangiliklaridan xabardor bo‘lishdagi qiyinchiliklar, ayniqsa ta‘til paytida va bo‘sh vaqtlarida tengdoshlari bilan muloqot qilishda yuzaga keladigan muammolar keltiriladi. Natijalar barcha talabalarning ta‘lim texnologiyalaridan teng foydalanish imkoniyatini ta‘minlash siyosatni ishlab chiqish va amaliy yechimlarni o‘z ichiga olgan strategik yondashuvni qo‘llab-quvvatlagan holda, oliy o‘quv yurtlari tomonidan raqamli texnologiyalarning mavjudligini doimiy ravishda baholash va yaxshilash zarurligini ta‘kidlaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: raqamli bo‘shliq, ta‘lim tengligi, qishloq ta‘limi, raqamli mavjudlik, oliy ta‘lim.

Introduction:

The digital divide refers to the disparities in access to digital resources and technology, which directly impact students' educational opportunities [2]. Addressing this divide is crucial for ensuring that all segments of the population have equal educational opportunities, regardless of their location or economic situation.

Higher education institutions (HEIs) are increasingly dependent on online resources, presenting them with the challenge of maintaining digital accessibility. This requires students to continually update and refine their digital infrastructure and the accessibility of their courses. HEIs need a thorough approach that includes regular reviews of digital resources, such as learning management systems and course materials, to find and fix any access issues. They must also develop a comprehensive digital strategy that involves creating institutional policies. This strategy should not only focus on adopting new digital tools and processes but also on ensuring that all students are able to effectively use these resources [2].

In Uzbekistan, specific barriers that students encounter in accessing educational resources online were identified through qualitative research conducted at the Russian State University of Oil and Gas named after Gubkin in Tashkent. This study provides insights into the challenges students face when trying to access study materials over the Internet.

Literature Review:

Research shows that having access to modern educational technologies can greatly enhance the quality of education, opening doors to personal and professional development. However, the lack of uniform access to these technologies presents major challenges.

The term "digital divide" refers to the unequal access to digital resources and technology, which significantly impacts economic opportunities, educational achievements, and the ability to participate in digital governance. In India, initiatives such as the Digital India Mission and BharatNet are being implemented to boost infrastructure and digital literacy, which will improve connectivity and access to educational resources. Meanwhile, Finland prioritizes high-quality, accessible digital educational tools, especially for students with disabilities, addressing both the technical and social aspects of digital accessibility [2]. According to Rao et al., this digital inequality not only mirrors but also intensifies existing social and economic disparities, limiting individual potential and hindering overall societal progress [8]. Orekhov and Chubarov examine the wider implications, noting how disparities in access can deepen social inequalities and restrict personal and societal development. They argue for better access to digital technologies, equal participation in the digital economy, and strong data privacy protections to promote digital justice [6]. These perspectives highlight different approaches to tackling digital inclusion: India's focus

on infrastructure, Finland's emphasis on quality and accessibility, and the broader socio-philosophical issues affecting digital equity.

Looking at the strategies India and Finland use to bridge the digital divide reveals several approaches that could also benefit Uzbekistan. India focuses heavily on expanding digital infrastructure, with projects like BharatNet, which aims to connect rural areas with a fiber-optic network. Finland, on the other hand, concentrates on developing accessible and user-friendly digital resources for distance learning, ensuring that education is inclusive and accessible for students with special needs. For Uzbekistan, adapting these strategies to local conditions could be key. It's crucial to develop telecommunications infrastructure in regional areas and to introduce educational technologies that meet the unique needs of Uzbek students, taking into account linguistic and cultural diversity.

Methodology and Research Design

The qualitative study was conducted to investigate the difficulties encountered by students from Gubkin University who live in rural and remote areas, with a specific focus on digital connectivity issues. The research aimed to delve into how the digital divide affects the educational experiences of these students. By undertaking this study, the objective was to gain a deep and detailed understanding of the obstacles that rural students face in accessing digital education. This understanding is intended to be the first step in developing focused interventions to help overcome the digital divide in higher education.

Participant Selection

Participants were chosen through purposive sampling to focus on students most affected by significant digital divide issues due to their rural locations. The selection criteria included students who are currently enrolled at Gubkin University and live in areas identified as rural or known for connectivity challenges. A total of 60 students participated in the study, providing a broad representation from various rural areas such as Vobkent in the Bukhara region, Akmangit in the Nukus region, Almalik and Qibray in the Tashkent region, and Urgut in the Samarkand region.

Data Collection Methods

Data was gathered through face-to-face interviews, facilitating a deeper and more personal interaction with the participants. Each interview took place in a quiet room on the university campus to ensure privacy and minimize external distractions. The interviews, lasting between 45 to 60 minutes, followed a semi-structured format. This approach used an interview guide with open-ended questions, allowing a comprehensive exploration of the students' experiences. The study was ethically approved by Gubkin University's institutional review board. Before the interviews, participants were briefed on the study's purpose and the confidentiality of their responses. Each participant provided written informed consent, which included permission to record the interviews to ensure accurate data transcription.

Questions for interview: The interview included questions about daily internet usage, experiences with online learning, the financial burden of internet access, and the emotional and academic impact of connectivity issues. The whole document with questions may be found at: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1OfhHWb6_2HgCCkL9Dt03oF6JKWxNCBk-OwRLTQow-7U/edit?usp=sharing

Data Analysis: Interviews were audio-recorded with participant consent and transcribed verbatim. The transcripts were analyzed for recurring themes using thematic analysis, facilitated

by NVivo software, which helped organize the data and align emerging themes with the research objectives.

Validation and Reliability: To enhance the reliability and validity of the study, several strategies were employed:

Member Checking: After analyzing the initial data, participants were presented with a summary of the findings to verify the accuracy of the interpretations made from their interviews [4].

Triangulation: To ensure the robustness of the findings, the study used data triangulation by comparing interview results with existing research on digital divides in similar educational contexts around the world. This method is widely recognized for its effectiveness in gathering qualitative data [1], [7].

Researcher Reflexivity: Throughout the study, the researcher kept a reflexive journal to note any personal biases and thoughts about the interview process. This practice helped in preserving objectivity and addressing any potential biases in the study [3].

Findings: The findings are derived from a thorough thematic analysis of the interview transcripts. Several key themes emerged, highlighting significant challenges:

Poor Connectivity: Students experienced extremely slow internet speeds, with some reporting that downloading a single e-book could take hours. This severely hindered their ability to effectively access and use online learning resources.

Limited Access During Holidays: During holiday periods, students faced difficulties in maintaining connections with classmates and engaging in group studies or projects. This issue was more pronounced when they returned to remote family homes, where internet services were even less reliable.

Barriers to Self-Education: Many students expressed a strong desire for self-education through online platforms and resources. However, they felt frustrated by the limited bandwidth, which restricted their ability to explore educational content, watch tutorial videos, or participate in online courses.

Difficulty Accessing University Updates: Staying informed about university news and events was a significant challenge. Students felt disconnected from the university community because they could not access updates about events or important administrative announcements, which their urban counterparts could easily obtain online.

Accessing Additional Materials: There was a notable disparity in accessing additional learning materials. While urban students could quickly receive extra materials from teachers via instant messaging platforms, rural students faced difficulties with simple downloads, making it challenging to keep up with coursework and supplementary learning.

Conclusion: The findings highlight a significant digital divide that affects rural students' academic performance, social integration, and personal development. The challenges are complex and impact multiple aspects of their educational experience, including access to materials, communication with peers, and involvement in university life. These issues necessitate targeted interventions from educational institutions and policymakers. By enhancing digital infrastructure in rural areas, these interventions can ensure equitable access to educational opportunities and promote a more inclusive academic environment for all students.

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